

Tuning Porosity of Reduced Graphene Oxide Membrane Materials by Alkali Activation

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Abstract: The alkali-activation method allows for obtaining highly porous carbon materials. In this study, we explored the effect of activation temperature and potassium hydroxide concentration on the pore structure of reduced graphene oxide (rGO), as potential membrane material. Above 700°C, potassium species react with the carbon plane of rGO to form nanopores. This activation process is deeply studied through DSC measurements and isothermal gravimetric analysis. The porosity of the formed materials consists of both micro- and mesopores, with most of the pores having a size smaller than 10 nm. The specific surface area and pore volume increase with increasing the potassium hydroxide/graphene oxide weight ratio (KOH/GO) up to 7 (897 m²·g⁻¹ and 0.97 cm³·g⁻¹, respectively). However, for a synthesis mixture with KOH/GO of 10, the specific surface area of the produced material drops to 255 m²·g⁻¹. The film-forming ability of the porous reduced graphene oxide (PRGO) was tested by drop-casting on porous silicon carbide substrates. In this case, continuous PRGO films were obtained only from dispersions with 5 g·L⁻¹ GO loading and KOH/GO ≤3. Such films can still have high specific surface area and pore volume (up to 528 m²·g⁻¹ and 0.53 cm³·g⁻¹) and main pore volume <10 nm. Hence, they can potentially be applied as membrane devices, but their scalability and their adhesion on the substrate under realistic filtration conditions still remain challenges.

Keywords: graphene oxide; potassium hydroxide; thermal activation; membrane materials